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Effects of Speed Endurance Training on Agility and Functional Performance in Soccer Players

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: To determine the effects of speed endurance training on agility and functional performance of soccer players.

Methods: A Randomized Control Trial (RCT) was conducted at Pakistan sports board (PSB), utilizing convenience sampling techniques for the selection of 44 soccer athletes. These participants were then divided into Group A and Group B. In Group A (interventional), athletes underwent conventional training alongside Speed Endurance Production (SEP) Training, while Group B (Control) received only conventional training. The assessment of outcomes included the T- Test for agility, a 40-meter sprint test for speed endurance, and the Yo-Yo Intermittent Recovery Test Level 2 for functional performance. Baseline measurements were taken on the first day, with post-training assessments conducted after the 8th week. The collected data were analyzed using SPSS software version 25.

Results: Post-training comparison of agility, speed endurance and functional performance between Group A and Group B has shown that there was a significant post-training difference in all these variables between both groups as $p < 0.05$ for all. The post-training mean score for agility test was 9.46 ± 0.54 seconds in Group A, while 9.97 ± 0.62 seconds in Group B, mean 40-meter sprint test score was 4.93 ± 0.19 seconds in Group A and 5.17 ± 0.34 seconds for Group B, mean Yo-Yo IR 2 score was 729.00 ± 56.65 meters in Group A and 648.00 ± 43.48 meters in Group B.

Conclusion: Speed endurance training along with conventional training is better than conventional training alone in improving agility, speed, endurance, and functional performance in the soccer players.

INTRODUCTION:

Football or soccer is an arduous sport that needs a special assembly of technical skills, tactical awareness, and physical ability. Agility is essential in soccer to outdo opposing players and execute fast, accurate actions. ^[1,2] Functional performance includes several physical characteristics such as speed, power, endurance and coordination that collectively determine field efficiency. ^[3] Speed endurance training has therefore become an increasingly popular means of increasing these fundamental pillars in the performance fabrication for soccer players. With the advancement of soccer, need for speed and agility in soccer players has become vital than ever before. ^[4]

Speed endurance training (SET) has emerged as a specialized training approach. This form of training extends beyond the usual focus on cardiovascular endurance and including factors that directly complement a player's effectiveness in maneuvering from one point to another during game. ^[5] SET involves running at a high but sustainable intensity. The objective is to boost the athlete's anaerobic capacity and lactic acid tolerance allowing him/her to maintain high speed for a long period. ^[6] Agility is a critical aspect of soccer, requiring players to make rapid changes in direction while maintaining control over their movements. ^[7] SET includes drills that focus on agility, helping players develop the ability to change direction swiftly. ^[6] Soccer is not only about running—it entails technical skills in handling the ball, as dribbling, and passing. Speed endurance training acknowledges the relevance of these skills and includes drills that improve a player's capability in holding on to the ball while running at high speeds. ^[8] The balanced emphasis on fast play and ball control develops players with a broad array of skills, which include more effective offensive or defensive units. ^[9]

Recent developments in biotechnology have greatly increased our understanding of the complex signaling pathways that cause skeletal muscle to adapt to exercise. Researchers have conducted studies demonstrating how certain training methodologies can effectively activate the transcription of specific genes that play a pivotal role in enhancing physiological systems, thereby overcoming limitations in various athletic performances. ^[10]

Speed endurance maintenance training involves performing high-intensity sprints for a short period of time, followed by a shorter rest period. The work-to-rest ratio is usually between 1:2 and 1:3. ² This type of training is useful for athletes who need to maintain high speeds for longer periods of time, such as soccer players. Speed endurance production training involves performing high-intensity sprints for a longer period, followed by a longer rest period. The work- to-rest ratio is usually between 1:4 and 1:6. ² This type of training is useful for athletes who need to produce high speeds for shorter periods of time, such as sprinters. ^[11]

The purpose of this research was to determine the effects of speed endurance training on agility and functional performance in soccer players and to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between speed endurance training and the development of agility and functional performance in soccer players. The findings from this study can contribute to the existing body of knowledge surrounding sports performance and training methodology, offering valuable insights for coaches and trainers seeking to optimize their athletes' physical capabilities. Furthermore, this research has the potential to guide the development of evidence-based training protocols, enabling soccer players to improve their agility, functional performance, and overall, on-field effectiveness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and population

It was a single blinded Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT). The trial was registered on ClinicalTrials.gov prior to initiation of study, with the registration number NCT06131073. The study was conducted at Pakistan Sports Board (PSB). The study was completed within 6 months, from 15 July, 2023 to 15 November, 2023. Sample size was calculated through G*power software version 3.1 using Yo-Yo IR2 performance outcome measure for physical performance. ^[12] Effect size of 1.07 was calculated by using mean \pm SD of variable

Yo-Yo IR2 performance. Mean \pm SD in group 1 was 978 ± 57 m and in group 2 was 858 ± 48 m. ^[12] By keeping the level of significance at 0.05 and power at 95% calculated sample size was 40 (20 subjects in each group). Non-probability convenient sampling technique was used to recruit the soccer players.

Selection Criteria

This study included male soccer players, aged between 15 and 30 years were considered. Soccer athletes who had been actively playing for a period ranging from six months to one year were part of the study. Soccer players with specific injuries such as ankle sprain, meniscal injury, and hamstring strain were excluded. And participants with any long-term injuries, such as fractures of lower extremity bones were also excluded.

Data Collection Procedure

The data was collected from XXX, after taking consent from the soccer athletes. A total sample size of 44 was evaluated according to eligibility criteria and those who met the inclusion criteria were added in the study. Subjects were randomly allocated into two groups using (www.randomizer.org) a computer software. After that allocation list was made and through sealed opaque envelop method, 1 was labelled for group A and 2 was labelled for group B. Group A (Interventional) was given SEP training along with conventional training. Group B (Control) was given conventional training. Both Group A and B adhered to a standardized conventional training program conducted three days a week over an 8-week period. The training regimen included the following components:

A standardized 10-minute warm-up consisting of jogging. ^[13]

Multidirectional dynamic stretching of lower extremity muscles (Hamstring, Quadriceps Calf), with each stretch lasting 30 seconds. ^[11]

Preliminary jumping exercises, such as submaximal ankle and squat jumps, were incorporated for all soccer players before the commencement of the regime. ^[11]

Various exercises were introduced, including squats, Nordic hamstrings, core rotations, barbell rowing, lunges, hamstring kicks, side-way lunges, standing chest press, crunches (with a 90-second rest interval), core rotations, bounding jumps, and fast-shifting lunges. ^[14]

Each exercise session comprised 3 sets of 10 repetitions, with a 90-second rest provided after each exercise. This comprehensive training routine was implemented three times a week for the entire 8-week duration. ^[15]

SEP was given in Group A along with conventional regime. It was given 3 days/week. The SEP protocol in this study involved executing 6–8 repetitions of 20-second all-out bouts, with each repetition followed by 120 seconds of passive recovery. Within each 20-second bout, participants performed single shuttle runs covering approximately 140–150 meters (comprising 70–75 meters followed by another 70–75 meters, depending on the assigned group), exerting their maximal effort throughout. The SEP protocol was administered three times per week over the course of eight weeks. ^[16]

Data Collection Tools

Yo-Yo Intermittent Recovery Test Level 2 (Yo-Yo IR2): The present study utilized the Yo-Yo Intermittent Recovery Test Level 2 to assess athletes' performance. This test was designed to evaluate an athlete's ability to engage in vigorous intermittent aerobic exercise with a significant anaerobic component. Specifically, the variant of the Yo-Yo test employed in this study is commonly utilized for gauging the aerobic capacity of adult athletes at the elite and professional levels. To conduct the test, specific equipment is required, including a suitable facility with consistent, flat, and non-slip terrain (with a minimum length of 30 meters), marking cones, measuring tape (greater than 30 meters), and a performance recording sheet. The test protocol consists of 91 shuttles and has a duration of approximately 29 minutes. Results from the test can be expressed in two ways: **total distance covered (in meters)** and the calculation of **VO₂ max**, providing comprehensive insights into the athletes' aerobic capabilities. ^[17] The validity of Yo-Yo IR2 is $r =$

0.02 to -0.72 .^[18] The reliability for distance part is Intra-class correlation coefficients (ICCs) between 0.87 and 0.95, and for heart rate responses ICCs between 0.73 and 0.97.^[19]

2. Agility T-test: The T-Test is a simple agility assessment designed for athletes, encompassing forward, lateral, and backward movements, making it applicable to a diverse array of sports. To conduct this test, minimal equipment is needed, including a tape measure, marking cones, and a stopwatch. The test evaluates an athlete's ability to navigate various directional changes, providing a practical measure of agility relevant to a broad spectrum of athletic activities.^[18] The validity of the agility test is $r = 0.936$ to $r = 0.987$ ^[14] and the reliability of agility T-Test is ICC = 0.86 and 0.82.^[20]

3. 40 meters Sprint Test: Sprint or speed assessments can be conducted over different distances, depending on the specific factors being evaluated and their relevance to the sport in question. For assessing acceleration, the time taken for the first 10 meters or yards from a stationary start is measured, while a 40-meter distance can be utilized as an indicator of speed endurance. Participants are typically allowed three trials, and the best time achieved is recorded, rounded to the nearest two decimal places, providing a comprehensive evaluation of both acceleration and speed endurance.^[21] The reliability of sprint test range between ICC=0.968 to 0.989.^[22]

Statistical Analysis

The statistical software IBM SPSS Statistics SPSS 25.0 was used for analysis. Shapiro wilk was used to assess the normality, p value was greater than 0.05 showing that data was distributed normally. So parametric tests were applied for within and between group comparison. A paired t- test was used for within group analysis. Independent t-Test was used for between two group's analyses.

A CONSORT flowchart showing the flow of participants through the phases of trials is shown in

Figure 1.

Figure 1: CONSORT diagram

RESULTS

The mean age of participants in Group A was 21.75 ± 3.76 and in Group B was 21.85 ± 3.37 as shown in **Table 1**. The mean BMI in Group A was 20.87 ± 1.38 and in Group B was 21.02 ± 1.39 as shown in **Table 2**. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess the normality of data, being the sample size less than 50 and it revealed that all p values were more than 0.05, indicating a normal distribution of data.

Table 1: Age of Participants in Group A and Group B

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age in Group A	20	15.00	29.00	21.75	3.76
Age in Group B	20	16.00	30.00	21.85	3.37

Table 2: Body Mass Index (BMI) of Participants in Group A and in Group B

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
BMI in Group A	20	19.00	23.00	20.87	1.38
BMI in Group B	20	19.00	23.50	21.02	1.39

Comparison between both groups using independent t-test has revealed that at baseline comparison between both groups there was no significant difference as $p > 0.05$ for all variables, suggesting that the groups were similar at the start of the study, as shown in **Table 3**. However, post-training comparison of agility with T-Test, speed endurance with 40-meter sprint test and functional performance with Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test between Group A and Group B has shown that there was significant post-training difference in all these variables between both groups as $p < 0.05$ for all. The post-training mean score for T-test was 9.46 ± 0.54 seconds in Group A, while 9.97 ± 0.62 seconds in Group B, mean 40-meter sprint test score was 4.93 ± 0.19 seconds in Group A and 5.17 ± 0.34 seconds for Group B, mean Yo-Yo IR 2 score was 729.00 ± 56.65 meters in Group A and 648.00 ± 43.48 meters in Group B, showing that speed endurance training along with conventional training is better than conventional training alone in improving agility, speed endurance and functional performance in the soccer players as shown in **Table 4**.

Table 3: Baseline Comparison of Agility, Speed Endurance and Functional Performance between Group A and Group B

Variable	Group	Mean \pm S.D.	Mean difference	95% CI Lower, Upper	p-value
Pre training Agility T-Test	Speed Endurance Production Training Group	10.37 ± 0.61	0.01	-0.40, 0.37	0.93

	Conventional training Group	10.38±0.60			
Pre training Speed Endurance 40- meter sprint test	Speed Endurance Production Training Group	5.54±0.28	0.10	-0.90, 0.29	0.28
	Conventional training Group	5.44±0.31			
Pre training Functional Performance Yo- Yo intermittent recovery test level 2	Speed Endurance Production Training Group	592.35±49.10	1.50	-32.52, 29.52	0.95
	Conventional training Group	593.85±47.80			

Table 4: Post-training Comparison of Agility, Speed Endurance and Functional Performance between Group A and Group B

Variables	Group	Mean± S.D.	Mean difference	95% CI Lower, Upper	p-value
Post training Agility T- Test	Speed Endurance Production Training Group	9.46±0.54	0.51	-0.88, -0.13	<0.01
	Conventional training Group	9.97±0.62			
Post training Speed Endurance 40- meter sprint test	Speed Endurance Production Training Group	4.93±0.19	0.23	-0.41, -0.59	0.01
	Conventional training Group	5.17±0.34			

Post training Functional Performance Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 2	Speed Endurance Production Training Group	729.00±56.65	81.00	48.67, 113.32	<0.01
	Conventional training Group	648.00±43.48			

DISCUSSION

The findings of the current study are consistent with the previous literature highlighting the benefits of speed endurance training in improving agility, endurance, and functional performance. The SEP protocol consisted of intense shuttle runs (140–150m) with 120 seconds of rest between each set along with conventional training involving multi directional stretching and strengthening exercises which resulted in better acceleration, maximal sprint speed and general agility.

Trecroci et al. observed improvements in both physical and mental performance in soccer players after nonspecific speed and agility training.^[13] In our study, the mean differences in agility, as measured by the T-test, revealed a significant improvement of 0.91 seconds in Group A and 0.41 seconds in Group B after speed endurance and conventional training, respectively. These improvements align with the notion that targeted speed endurance training positively influences agility, as reflected in reduced T-test scores.

Clemente et al.'s meta-analysis highlighted the multifaceted benefits of small-sided games (SSGs) in soccer. While our study did not directly incorporate SSGs, the mean differences in functional performance, particularly in the Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 2, were substantial. Group A showed an impressive mean difference of 136.65 meters, and Group B demonstrated a noteworthy improvement of 54.15 meters. These findings underscore the positive impact of speed endurance and conventional training on functional performance, showcasing their effectiveness in a manner comparable to SSGs.^[15]

The study by Fransson et al. compared the responses to speed endurance runs training and small-sided game training, emphasizing the significant enhancement in exercise performance. In our study, the mean differences in the 40-meter sprint test further support the effectiveness of speed endurance training. Group A exhibited a mean difference of 0.61 seconds, while Group B showed a notable improvement of 0.26 seconds. These outcomes align with the broader theme of improved sprint performance observed in their research.^[23]

Iaia et al. investigated the effects of speed endurance production (SEP) and speed endurance maintenance (SEM) training on soccer player performance. While our study did not explicitly categorize training into SEP and SEM, the mean differences in agility and functional performance collectively reflect positive outcomes similar to their findings. The mean difference of 0.51 seconds in the T-test for Group A and the mean difference of 81.00 meters in the Yo-Yo IR 2 for Group A underscore the positive impact of speed endurance training on both agility and endurance.^[24]

Both techniques showed significant improvements in improving speed endurance and agility, however post-training comparison of agility with T-Test, speed endurance with 40-meter sprint test and functional performance with Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test between Group A and Group B has shown that there was significant post-training difference in all these variables between both groups as $p < 0.05$ for all. The post-training mean score for T-test was 9.46 ± 0.54 seconds in Group A, while 9.97 ± 0.62 seconds in Group B, mean 40-meter sprint test score was 4.93 ± 0.19 seconds in Group A and 5.17 ± 0.34 seconds for Group B, mean Yo-Yo IR 2 score was 729.00 ± 56.65 meters in Group A and 648.00 ± 43.48 meters in Group B, showing that speed endurance training along with conventional training is better than conventional training alone in improving agility, speed endurance and functional performance in the soccer players. Our

research helps fill the gap in existing literature as it supports positive changes brought about by speed endurance training on agility and functional performance among soccer players. Changes in the key performance indicators are either on par with or exceed those reported elsewhere, which suggests that speed endurance training is an impactful targeted method to advance soccer player development.

The strength of the study makes it an important source for information about speed endurance exercise within soccer players. Second, it enables one to comprehend the effects of speed endurance training on agility and functional performance. In addition, the use of a randomized controlled design enhances internal validity by eliminating sources of bias when inferring causality. It is a broad spectrum that encompasses agility, speed endurance and functional performance as an integrated assessment to provide the overall picture of training. In addition, linking findings to relevant literature in the discussion section enhances context by integrating information with established research and provides practical suggestions for coaches, leaders, and trainers.

Limitations and Recommendations: Despite its strengths, the study faces certain limitations that warrant consideration. The size of the sample, especially two groups (Group A and Group B), is limited in generalization thus compromising the results derived. A relatively short period of training does not allow us to draw conclusions about sustainability or on long-term effects from changes observed. The limitation of the case under study to a single site may limit its applicability in terms of subject or playing conditions. Moreover, the study does not control individual training backgrounds and inadequate detailing of underlying mechanisms limits an extensive understanding of how speed endurance training alters agility and functional performance. Cognitive or mental assessment of the players were not done, which might have affected their capacity to engage in the study. These limitations should be addressed in future research to improve the study's reliability and external validity.

CONCLUSION

This research, therefore, concludes that speed endurance training has a significant impact on agility and functional performance in soccer players. The results validate the practical utilization of this select training approach for coaches and trainers who are seeking to enhance a player's potential. Although recognizing strengths of the study, including its randomized controlled design and broad evaluation parameters, it highlights future studies that will need to overcome shortcomings as well as explore causal mechanisms and individual's training background.

Conflict of Interest: None

Participants consent: Informed consent was taken from all participants before starting the training or data collection.

Use of AI: None

Authors' Contribution: MRK contributed to the conception and study design. MRK and SR contributed to data collection, MRK and SR contributed to data analysis and interpretation, FI contributed to article drafting and MRK contributed to proofreading of the article. All authors read and approve the final version of the manuscript.

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